

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 2

 Acceptance of papers **FEBRUARY, 2025**

Acceptance of articles

Published every
monthly

Directions

Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

ISSN 3060-5229

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t.me/scopus_IST2100

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JOURNAL "INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY" HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

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THE SYSTEM OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC METHODS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF ENERGY SECTOR ENTERPRISES AND ITS KEY COMPONENTS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the organizational and economic mechanisms for enhancing the efficiency of energy industry enterprises and their key components. The focus is on research in areas such as the sustainable development of the energy sector, the organization of energy production under resource constraints using digital and AI-based technologies, competitiveness improvement, and economic support for enterprises' effective functioning.

Key words: organizational and economic mechanism, efficiency improvement, digital technologies, artificial intelligence, competitiveness enhancement.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, special importance is attached to the introduction of effective organizational and economic mechanisms in the development of the energy sector. This implies the rational use of available resources and targeted demand satisfaction in the context of utilizing innovative technologies. As part of scientific research, increasing attention is being paid to improving mechanisms for stimulating high-tech production, optimizing power, oil, and gas supply systems, as well as ensuring a reliable and uninterrupted supply of heat and electricity to consumers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In a market economy characterized by effective functioning and high competition, considerable attention is paid to developing organizational and economic methods aimed at improving the efficiency of energy enterprises. These methods should be comprehensive, integrating various measures into a unified mechanism to achieve optimal results. In this regard, the concept of an "organizational and economic mechanism for improving enterprise efficiency" emerges. For a more detailed understanding of the process of increasing an enterprise's efficiency, it is necessary to study such concepts as "mechanism," "economic mechanism," and "organizational mechanism," as well as analyze their interrelation and interaction within the framework of the organizational and economic mechanism.

According to the definition given by S.I. Ozhegov and N.Ya. Shvedov, a mechanism is an internal structure of a device, machine, or apparatus that ensures its operation. In a broader sense, this term can be considered a system or tool that regulates the order of functioning, the sequence of actions, and the processes necessary for implementing a particular phenomenon.

Yu.M. Osipov argues that nature and all its components are organized, and a system is an orderly formation. The mechanism, in turn, is an element of the system embedded within it, ensuring its holistic functioning. [2]

For a more comprehensive understanding of the term "economic mechanism," it is important to refer to modern economic research and existing approaches to its definition. According to S. Kamenitser, the economic mechanism is a system of methods and forms of interaction between business entities and the state, as well

as between various production structures. Its goal is to create favorable conditions and incentives to increase productivity and improve the population's standard of living.

One of the most challenging aspects of the economic mechanism is determining its objective basis—namely, the actual economic activity—which can be analyzed and regulated using the tools of the economic mechanism.

Additionally, it should be noted that the economic mechanism includes various components, such as organizational structures, management methods, legal norms, and other elements. Assessing their compliance with modern economic processes is crucial, as this plays a key role in ensuring the economic mechanism's effective functioning. In his works on the economic mechanism, P.G. Bunich emphasizes that achieving high production efficiency is the main condition for the successful functioning of this mechanism. [1] In this case, efficiency is regarded as the primary criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of an economic process.

Yu.M. Osipov considers the economic mechanism a complex social system, including economic entities, each of which has built-in management mechanisms. The interaction of these entities is carried out through socio-economic institutions that form a unified system and regulate the activities of participants in the economic process. [2]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of this study is the work of domestic and foreign scientists involved in the study of organizational and economic mechanisms for improving the efficiency of enterprises in the energy sector. The analysis used regulatory legal acts governing industry activities, as well as materials from scientific and practical conferences devoted to this topic. The research was based on a systematic approach, employing methods of logical, comparative, and statistical analysis to achieve its goals.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In modern economics, there is no single, universally recognized definition of the concepts of “organizational mechanism” and “economic mechanism.” In this regard, we analyze the works of both domestic and foreign economists researching these concepts to identify the key ideas embedded in these terms and, on this basis, develop our own approach to their definition.

One perspective considers the organizational mechanism as a tool for classifying tasks and building a hierarchical structure that unites them into a single system [2]. However, since this definition primarily focuses on fixing and ensuring the material aspects of an organizational mechanism, it is difficult to relate it to a broader understanding of this term, which includes not only material but also managerial and economic components.

According to Yu.M. Osipova, the organizational mechanism is a set of methods and organizational forms aimed at creating, developing, and optimizing production processes. It covers not only the individual elements of production but also the ways of their structuring, the interrelationships between components, and legal norms and organizational structures that ensure the effective functioning of the production system [2].

Alexander Bukreev and Yuri Osipov believe that the organizational mechanism consists of various forms of management that ensure the stable operation of an enterprise [8]. In turn, Stanislav Kamenitzer considers the mechanism of organizational management as a system of administrative measures aimed at increasing the efficiency and productivity of production [9].

The organizational management mechanism is focused on increasing productivity and includes various methods such as improving the management structure, effective coordination of managers and specialists, recruitment and distribution of personnel, evaluation of their activities, work motivation, provision of technical and information support, regulation of management processes, and control over their execution.

In his work “A Brief Outline of the Main Economic Mechanisms”, French researcher Charles Rist [10] examines the concept of the economic mechanism and expresses his views on its study. In his opinion, simply recognizing the existence of economic mechanisms is already an important step in understanding them.

S. Kamenitzer considers the economic management mechanism as a set of measures aimed at stimulating the economic interests of both individual employees and labor collectives in order to increase productivity. This opinion largely echoes the point of view of Charles Rist, who argued that economic mechanisms exist and can be identified in the analysis process. [9]

According to S. Kamenitzer, the main task of the economic mechanism is to increase the efficiency of producing high-quality products that not only meet the needs of the economy but also contribute to the long-term development of production processes.

A. M. Bukreev argues that the economic mechanism cannot be reduced solely to a system of financial incentives and material remuneration for employees. He believes that the economic mechanism is a complex

system that includes various forms and management procedures at different levels. Thus, the economic mechanism covers not only financial instruments but also other management methods that ensure the stable and efficient functioning of the enterprise. [12]

Economic processes develop spontaneously, following a certain sequence that leads to specific results depending on the nature of the initial event. This means that the economic mechanism is determined by both the initial conditions and the outcome of the chain of events. Thus, according to A. Kuhlman [13], the number of possible economic mechanisms depends on the characteristics of the initial impulse and the conditions under which it is formed.

According to theoretical provisions, the number of economic mechanisms is determined by the number of impulses that initiate the formation of interconnected systems, as well as the number of existing relationships within these systems. The multiplication of these two parameters leads to a significant number of possible variations, which indicates a variety of economic mechanisms.

V. P. Moskalenko points out that the traditional view of the economic mechanism as a system does not sufficiently take into account key aspects such as the interaction between elements, their organizational arrangement, financial and investment processes, and the management subsystem. In his work, he emphasizes that the economic mechanism is a complex system that ensures the continuity of economic processes and includes a network of interrelated economic strategies organized in a hierarchical order. Within this system, there are separate subsystems such as activity analysis, planning, control, and staff motivation.

In practice, many organizational and economic mechanisms are used to achieve various goals. These include methods of managing technological transport, business combinations, coordination of financial and industrial groups, and other similar mechanisms.

If we consider the task of increasing the productivity of an enterprise, we can identify a system of interrelated activities implemented through certain forms and methods of management. The organizational and economic mechanism for improving the efficiency of an enterprise (OEMEPEF) focuses on optimizing the work of an enterprise at all levels of management and in various directions. It is a set of measures covering both organizational and economic aspects and requires a clear structure, as well as competent implementation using appropriate management tools. [14]

The organizational and economic mechanism aimed at improving an enterprise's efficiency comprises several interrelated subsystems. Key areas include the rational use of equipment and tools, increasing employee productivity, optimizing the movement of material resources, preparing production for new product launches, managing information flows, ensuring high product quality, and developing production infrastructure and logistics.

Additionally, this mechanism encompasses marketing research, operational planning, the formation of an optimal production structure, the regulation of internal economic relations, and the management of social processes within the enterprise. Each subsystem plays a crucial role, contributing specific functions that enable a comprehensive approach to enhancing enterprise efficiency.

To improve production efficiency, an economic mechanism must incorporate several essential functional subsystems, including performance analysis and evaluation, planning, control, and staff motivation.

Within the subsystem dedicated to improving labor organization efficiency in the production process, a broad range of tasks must be addressed. Achieving these objectives requires implementing measures such as staff professional development, workplace organization enhancement, labor process optimization, the establishment of reasonable labor standards, and introducing both material and non-material incentive systems for employees.

Moreover, for the effective development of production processes, a specialized subsystem must focus on optimizing operations by identifying and implementing the most efficient management methods and practices.

Enhancing enterprise efficiency demands that each element of the organizational and economic mechanism (OEMPE) be supported by appropriate resources. These resources include organizational, legal, investment, informational, regulatory, programmatic, logistical, mathematical, and methodological components. An economic mechanism designed to enhance enterprise performance can leverage various funding sources, both internal and external. To ensure the organization's sustainable operation, it is essential to secure access to credit facilities, subsidies, revenue from stock and foreign exchange market operations, and other financial instruments that contribute to the enterprise's stable development. For the effective functioning of the organizational and economic mechanism aimed at increasing enterprise efficiency, it is crucial to maximize the use of the information system. This system should incorporate all necessary components and ensure their seamless interaction, thereby creating a unified information environment.

In addition, the successful operation of the organizational and economic management process (OEMP) requires a reliable regulatory framework that includes standards and regulations governing labor costs, wages, inventory management, resource and equipment utilization, financial indicators, as well as material, fuel, and

energy expenditures. An essential element of this framework is the set of norms that regulate the use of production facilities within established deadlines. Socio-economic norms and standards also play a significant role, influencing not only enterprise efficiency but also its social responsibility toward society.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The effectiveness of an enterprise's activities directly depends on the full functionality of the organizational and economic mechanism for improving efficiency (OEMEPEF). To achieve the desired level of effectiveness, it is essential to focus on its continuous development and improvement.

It is important to note that OEMEPEF belongs to the category of microeconomic mechanisms, as it comprises a set of interrelated organizational and economic measures implemented at the enterprise level to enhance productivity.

One of the key characteristics of this mechanism is its emergence the ability of the entire system to exhibit properties that are not inherent in its individual components. This means that the coordinated interaction of all elements within the mechanism leads to a significant increase in business efficiency. Conversely, the isolated use of individual tools will not yield the same positive results.

The functioning of this mechanism is designed to enhance efficiency across all areas of enterprise operations by optimizing resource utilization and implementing advanced management solutions. The role of employees in executing organizational and economic measures is critical to achieving this goal.

The mechanism operates by establishing a clear relationship between system elements, structuring them, and defining their significance. It consists of a set of organizational and economic measures, along with the most suitable tools to ensure high-quality performance. This structured approach guarantees improved business efficiency across all aspects of the company's activities.

Ultimately, the primary goal of OEMEPEF is to develop a comprehensive set of organizational and economic measures that ensure timely production and product delivery according to established standards, while also promoting the rational use of enterprise resources. This section outlines the structure and content of the developed mechanism aimed at enhancing enterprise efficiency. The mechanism is based on a systematic approach and integrates a set of elements, including functional and supporting subsystems that operate in close coordination as a unified system.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 2

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